

MONITORING AND SIMULATION OF THE VACUUM INFUSION PROCESS

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1 Introduction

The vacuum infusion (VI) process [1] is a relatively cheap composite manufacturing process that is widely used for the manufacture of large-scale structures in a number of industries, in particular the aerospace, marine and wind turbine industries. Fig. 1 describes schematically the vacuum infusion process and the typical make-up of the assembled stack. Once the vacuum bag is sealed, the resin inlet is sealed and the air is extracted by means of a vacuum pump. This serves two purposes, firstly to compress the preform in order to achieve a part with a high fibre volume fraction and secondly to create a differential pressure to allow the infusion of the resin.

From the resin inlet to the vacuum vent, the preform thickness and the compaction pressure are affected due to the flexible nature of the vacuum bag. The preform has to be infused completely before the resin cures. Therefore, the monitoring of the process is very important to ensure the quality of the final composite part.

Analytical [2] and numerical [3] studies are extremely useful for understanding the entire manufacturing process and designing new products. Numerical simulations of resin infusion can assist in positioning the inlet and the vent, which is especially useful for large and complex parts. Various infusion strategies can be studied using a virtual model. This can reduce prototype testing and process set-up costs. Based on Darcy's law, many mould filling codes such as LIMS [4], Polyworks and PAM-RTM [5] have been developed in order to optimise manufacturing processes. It is essential to know the principal permeability values to compute the filling times in a simulation. In addition to the permeability information, the cure and the viscosity data of the

resin are needed for more realistic and accurate flow simulations.

In this study, a vacuum infusion process monitoring methodology with thermocouples and the simulation of the vacuum infusion process were studied for an unsaturated polyester resin system. Experimental studies were performed to determine the resin and the preform related parameters for the flow simulations. The VARI module of the PAM-RTM simulation package was used to simulate the filling times. Finally, the vacuum infusion experiments were conducted to validate the simulations.

2 Aims and Objectives

The global aim of the vacuum infusion process monitoring and the process simulation is to assess the processability of novel fire resistant co-blended resin systems composed of unsaturated polyester and phenolic resins [6]. The present study aims to investigate the processability of an unsaturated polyester resin system (Crystic 701 resin and 1% Methylethylketone Peroxide catalyst) in the vacuum infusion process forming a basis for the processability of the novel resin systems for the global project. This study focused on a thorough investigation of the vacuum infusion process by exploring the process and the material (the fibre and the resin) related parameters. The objectives of this study can be divided into seven main categories and they are listed below.

a- *Monitoring* of the vacuum infusion process incorporating thermocouples to monitor the fibre volume fraction, the flow rate, and the flow front advancement.

b- *Preform characterisation* involving an in-plane permeability measurement method to determine the

effective permeability values and the compressibility curve.

c- *Cure kinetics* study based on Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) data.

d- *Cure modelling* using the autocatalytic cure kinetics model.

e- *Cure simulation* using the DSC study results, the cure model and the thermal properties of the materials.

f- *Flow simulation* of the vacuum infusion process in PAM-RTM software using the preform and the resin data, and the boundary conditions.

g- *Validation* of the flow simulation results with the experimental results.

3 Process Monitoring Methodology

The vacuum infusion process monitoring setup (Fig. 2) included i) a vacuum infusion setup using a glass mould, ii) two high resolution cameras to monitor the flow front progression, iii) K type teflon insulated thermocouples to monitor the flow fronts inside the preform and measure the temperatures at various locations, iv) LVDTs to measure the thickness variations in different regions for the calculation of the fibre volume fractions, iv) a weighing scale to monitor the mass flow rate of resin, v) a vacuum pump with a pressure regulator, and vi) a National Instruments compact-rio as the data acquisition system and associated Labview software to record the data.

During the experiments, the thermocouples demonstrated their ability to detect the flow front advancement without needing a temperature difference between the resin, the mould and the reinforcement. This methodology is explained in Section 6. The thermocouples were also informative on the exothermic reaction during curing (Fig. 18).

4 Preform Characterisation

Due to the flexible nature of the vacuum bag, there is no direct control over the thickness (or the fibre

volume fraction) of the composite part in the vacuum infusion process. The compaction of the preform is dynamic and depends upon the compressibility and relaxation of the preform under pressure, and the interaction between the preform and the infusion liquid. This is distinctly different from Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) where thickness and fibre volume fraction can be controlled due to the rigid moulds.

For the characterisation of the preform, composed of twelve layers of triaxial non-crimp e-glass fabric (Table 1), the compaction rig (Fig. 4) was designed by the authors. It composed of a square base mould and a flat top platen. The compaction plate (top platen) was able to slide in the mould with no resistance. This rig was constructed for two purposes, i) the preform compressibility analysis and ii) the channel flow in-plane permeability measurements. Corn oil was used in the permeability experiments. The results of the preform characterisation study were the inputs in the numerical flow simulations in Section 7.

4.1 Compressibility

The compaction behaviour of the multi-layer preform was experimentally characterised using the compaction rig on an Instron 5569 testing machine fitted with a 50 kN load cell in force control mode. The preform (20cm x 20cm) was compressed at the rate of 2mm/min. Once the pressure reached 100kPa, the load was maintained for 30 minutes and fabric relaxation occurred (Fig. 3). The equation in Fig. 3 was obtained by plotting a power trendline up to the relaxation point.

4.2 Permeability

The in-plane (channel flow) unsaturated permeability measurements of the preform (15cm x 5cm) were performed using the compaction rig (Fig. 4) on an Instron 5569 testing machine. Instron machine provided precise top platen movement that controlled the fibre volume fraction accurately and precisely for the permeability measurements. Flexible closed-cell foam (dimensions of 19.5cm x 19.5cm) with an opening area of 16cm x 5cm was

placed in the base mould and the preform was placed in the gap. The thickness of the twelve-layer preform was nearly 12 mm and the thickness of the foam was 15 mm. The foam provided sealing while the preform was under compression. Due to the invisibility of the process, K type thermocouples (Fig. 4b) were used to monitor the flow front advancement in the rig. The principle of the thermocouple flow front monitoring methodology can be found in Section 6.

Due to the inhomogeneity of the preform, the permeability measurements were conducted in three different directions, shown in Fig. 5. In the tests, the fibre volume fractions for each orientation were 0.4, 0.48 and 0.6. The properties of the infusion liquid and the fabric used in the permeability measurements are given in Table 1.

For the permeability measurements, a vacuum pump was connected to the vent and the inlet was blocked to obtain a pressure gradient in the mould and infuse the corn oil through the preform. The procedure of the permeability measurement is listed below.

i) The preform was placed in the opening area of the foam, and the thermocouples were located inside the preform at the inlet and at the vent for the flow front monitoring.

ii) The top platen was lowered to obtain the desired fibre volume fraction. The following equation was used for the fibre volume fraction calculations.

$$V_f = \frac{W_f N}{h\rho} \quad (1)$$

where W_f is the areal weight of the fabric, N is the number of fabric layers in the preform, h is the thickness and ρ is the density of the fibres.

iii) Once the desired fibre volume fraction was achieved, the inlet was closed and the air was extracted with the help of the vacuum pump.

iv) The inlet was opened and the corn oil was infused through the fabric with the aid of the pressure difference between the atmospheric and the vacuum pressures. The vent pressure was 0.2 bar. The atmospheric pressure was measured using a

barometer. The flow was from the atmospheric pressure to the vacuum pressure in the mould.

v) The corn oil flow front was monitored using the thermocouples inside the mould during the flow and the flow travel time was recorded.

vi) The permeability was measured according to the (one-dimensional) equation [7] below.

$$K_{xx} = \frac{l^2 \mu \phi}{2\Delta P t} \quad (2)$$

where ΔP is the pressure differential between the inlet and the flow front, l is the flow front position, μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, ϕ is the porosity, t is the time.

The approach presented by Gebart and Lidstrom [8] was used to determine the principal permeability values (Fig. 6) from the effective permeability values that were experimentally measured. Table 2 presents the effective (K) and the principal permeability (K') values and the orientation angles for each fibre volume fraction.

As an example, Fig. 7 shows the filling time (Fig. 7a) and the resin pressure distribution (Fig. 7b) in the rig during a permeability test for the 90° oriented sample (fibre volume fraction of 60%). The principal permeability values (K'_{90} in the flow direction and K'_0 in widthwise), the infusion liquid, the fabric and the preform properties, and the boundary conditions were used to simulate the flow and the liquid pressure in the compaction rig. The preform was represented by solid elements and each layer was defined in the setup.

5 Curing Analysis

Crystic 701 [9] with a styrene content of 40-45% is a pre-accelerated, isophthalic polyester resin with low viscosity (1.6 poise) and controlled exotherm characteristics. The viscosity and exotherm characteristics of Crystic 701 make it particularly suitable for the manufacture of large structures in the vacuum infusion process. The recommended curing cycle of the laminates manufactured by Crystic 701 is for 24 hours at room temperature, and followed by a post-cure for 16 hours at 40°C or 3 hours at 80°C. The manufacturer recommends using the catalyst

between 1% (slow curing) and 2% (fast curing) by weight. 1% content was chosen for this work to provide the longest curing time and, therefore, to increase the processing time of the resin.

5.1 Cure Kinetics

In order to improve the accuracy of the flow simulations (in Section 7) and to do more realistic comparisons with the vacuum infusion experiments, the cure kinetics of the resin system was studied. The results of this study were used in the cure simulation in Section 5.2 and in the flow simulations in Section 7. The cure kinetics study of the unsaturated polyester resin system was based on DSC analyses. The measurement of the heat evolved during the curing reaction was conducted by means of a TA Instruments DSC Q2000 apparatus. The DSC analyses provided the heat flow versus time and temperature data. To investigate the ultimate heat of the reaction (H_U), the heat flow was measured for the heating ramps of 3°C, 5°C, 10°C and 20°C for the samples weighing 7mg (± 0.1) until 250°C. The information obtained from the dynamic runs did not depend on the heating rate, so an average result of 256 J/g was defined as the ultimate heat of reaction. Also, the isothermal tests were performed at the temperatures of 30°C, 40°C, 50°C, 60°C, 70°C and 80°C for the samples weighing 7mg (± 0.1). The details of the calculations can be found in references [10] and [11].

The conversion profiles for each isothermal test are shown in Fig. 8. As expected, the ultimate overall conversion increased with temperature. A graph of experimentally determined values of H_T/H_U versus temperature (T) is shown in Fig. 9. The ratio of H_T/H_U rose with temperature and was approximated by a piece-wise linear function of temperature as expressed by Eq. 3. The evolution of H_T/H_U was linear with the temperature until 50°C and almost levelled off after 50°C.

$$\frac{H_T}{H_U} = \begin{cases} 0.022 T(^{\circ}\text{C}) - 0.15 & T \leq 50^{\circ}\text{C} \\ \sim 1 & T > 50^{\circ}\text{C} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

As a result of the cure kinetics study, the autocatalytic equation (Eq. 4) represented the curing

of the unsaturated polyester resin system with the reaction orders of 0.43 and 3.87 for m and n , respectively. These were the inputs coupled with the thermal properties (Table 3) of the constituent materials for the cure simulation.

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = \left(109098 * \exp\left(\frac{-40730}{8.31*T}\right) \right) * \beta^m (1 - \beta)^n \quad (4)$$

here, 109098 (1/min) is the pre-exponential factor, 40730 (J/mol) is the activation energy, 8.31 (J/mol K) is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature, and $d\beta/dt$ is the rate of degree of cure.

5.2 Cure Simulation

The initial 24 hours curing stage was simulated in the curing module of PAM-RTM and compared with the DSC cure data in Fig. 10. In the simulations, the twelve-layer preform was represented by solid elements. One more layer was extruded around the solid mesh to represent the vacuum bag. The results of the cure kinetics study, the properties of the preform (density, areal weight, fibre volume fraction, and thickness), the vacuum bag, the mould and the resin were the inputs in the simulation. Fig. 11 shows the cure simulation results at randomly chosen times.

In the cure simulations, the role of $d\beta/dt$ and the material properties in the thermal phenomena are represented by the following equation:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_r c_{pr} \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T = \vec{\nabla} \cdot \{k \cdot \nabla T\} - \rho_r \Delta h \frac{d\beta}{dt} \quad (5)$$

here, T is the temperature, t is the time, ρ is the density, C_p is the specific heat, k is the heat conduction coefficient tensor, Δh is the total enthalpy of the polymerisation of the resin, α is the resin cure, and r represents the resin.

The differences between the DSC cure data and the simulation result can be attributed to the small quantity of resin used in the DSC test for the experimental cure analysis, but the cure simulation involved the resin and the reinforcement properties in the vacuum infusion process. The final cure results were close to each other, and the beginning of the cure simulation up to 3 hours was important

for the flow simulations. Normally, one can expect a very high exothermic temperature during the curing reaction of a thermoset resin system, but there was $\sim 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ increase in the temperature data (Fig. 18) in the vacuum infusion experiment due to the interaction of the resin with the preform on a large surface area.

5.3 Viscosity Analysis

The viscosity (measured by ICI viscometer) change over time was compared with a typical infusion time for a twelve-layer preform without using an infusion mesh (Fig. 12). The preform specification was same as the preform used in Section 6. The infusion mesh and the peel ply (Fig. 1) were not incorporated in the process to identify the maximum possible processing time for the resin. It can be seen that the viscosity was $0.19\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ in the beginning and it was $0.26\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ at the end of the filling. The infusion was completed just before the significant jump in the viscosity data.

6 Thermocouple Monitoring Methodology

Fig. 13 presents a twelve-layer fabric preform (length of 45cm and width of 15cm) infusion case study (vacuum pressure of 0.5 bar) without an infusion mesh. In this experiment, the preform consisted of alternate 0° and 90° orientation fabrics (Fig. 5) to obtain a more homogeneous structure. This structure was used to obtain an infusible preform for the flow front monitoring because other tests indicated that an entirely 90° oriented preform did not completely infuse (Fig. 20).

In order to monitor the flow fronts inside the laminate, seven thermocouples were located between the fourth and the fifth layers equally spaced, and a second set of seven thermocouples were located between the eighth and the ninth layers. The measurements were performed without a temperature difference between the resin and the mould. Typical flow front data is shown in Fig. 14. The thermocouple readings were almost identical with the camera recordings indicative of a uniform through thickness flow from inlet to vent. The data, plotted in Fig. 15, clearly shows the uniformity of the flow front through the thickness.

The experimental flow front locations detected by means of the cameras at three randomly chosen

times can be seen in Fig. 13. The top and the bottom flow front locations for the three cases were identical.

The response of the thermocouple sensing method was tested out of the mould in order to understand the interaction between the thermocouple and the liquid without a temperature difference at room temperature (Fig. 16). Two thermocouples, connected to a National Instruments Compact-Rio, were used in the test. One thermocouple was inserted through a small hole of a closed transparent container to isolate it and avoid its interaction with the surrounding air circulation in order to resemble the sealing of the thermocouples in the glass preform in the vacuum infusion process. The second thermocouple was out of the container, and measuring the ambient temperature.

The results presented in Fig. 17 demonstrate a clear temperature variation from the ambient temperature recording, while the temperature was relatively steady for the thermocouple recording within the pot. The pot, the liquid and the thermocouples were at room temperature before the test, and the conditions were the same during the test. The test procedure was: i) keeping one thermocouple out of the liquid but other one (case-1 in Fig. 16) in the pot and allowing the temperature data to reach a steady state in the container for ~ 90 seconds, and ii) dipping the thermocouple into corn oil manually (case-2 in Fig. 16). Once the thermocouple was dipped into the liquid a sudden drop occurred (Fig. 17). This behaviour was similar to the thermocouple flow front sensing in the vacuum infusion process, therefore providing evidence of the thermocouple acting as a flow front sensor.

The thermocouples were also informative on the exothermic reaction during the curing stage. Fig. 18, which is one thermocouple's full range of data from Fig. 14, shows the complete temperature data up to 21 hours after infusion. The resin reaches the maximum temperature after approximately 5 hours.

The change in thickness and the flow versus time data until the end of the filling are presented in Fig. 19. It can be seen that the thickness was higher at the vent and lower at the inlet region, and the flow rate was in a decreasing trend.

7 Flow Simulations

The inputs in the PAM-RTM simulation software were i) the preform characterisation data (the equations representing the principal permeability curves in Fig. 6, and the compressibility curve in Fig. 3), ii) the cure equation (Eq. 4), the enthalpy of the resin, and the viscosity data (Fig. 12), iii) the material properties (Table 3), and iv) the boundary conditions (inlet and vent pressures). A shell element (flow length of 45cm and width of 15cm) represented the preform in the simulations (Fig. 21 and Fig. 22).

In the simulations, the principal permeability directions were also defined. K_{90} was in the flow direction and K_0 was in the width direction for the 90° sample. These orientations were vice-versa for the 0° orientation sample.

In order to validate the numerical flow simulations, vacuum infusion experiments (with 0.5 bar vacuum pressure) with Crystic 701 resin were performed for two different samples (flow length of 45cm and width of 15cm). The first sample incorporated all the fabric layers in 0° orientation, whereas all the layers were in 90° orientation for the second sample (Fig. 5). The infusion result of the homogeneous preform was also included in Fig. 20 for a comparison with others. The total experimental filling time was nearly 11000 seconds for the homogeneous sample; it was nearly 4500 seconds for the 0° sample. The impregnation time was the longest (~13500 seconds) for 90° sample. Due to the resin gelation in ~13000 seconds (from Fig. 12), the resin flow stopped after nearly 75% flow front advancement for the 90° sample. The flow fronts were uniform for both 0° and 90° infusion cases and similar to the homogeneous sample used in Section 6.

The trend of the numerical and the experimental curves were similar to each other (Fig. 20). Similar to the experimental flow for the 90° sample, the flow front simulation stopped after 80% impregnation of the preform in ~13500 seconds (Fig. 21a). From here, the importance of using the curing behaviour of the resin system in the simulation can be seen.

The resin pressure and the fibre volume fraction distribution along the flow length of the preform can

be seen in Fig. 22. The fibre content was around 50% at the vent and it was around 42% at the inlet after the completion of the infusion.

8 Discussion

The resin, the preform and the vacuum infusion process related parameters were studied to inform the vacuum infusion simulations. The VARI module in PAM-RTM was used and the preform was represented by shell elements. The principal permeability equations, the compaction equation of the preform, the resin cure and viscosity data and the material properties were the inputs in the simulations. The simulation results were in good agreement with the vacuum infusion experiments.

A flow front monitoring method using cost-effective thermocouples was presented, which did not require a temperature difference between the resin and the mould. This method provided a three-dimensional flow front profile at room temperature. This method validated the uniform flow front from inlet to vent through the samples used in this study. A thermocouple-dipping test was conducted to validate the flow front detection behaviour of the thermocouples in the infusion process.

Preform characterisation was studied to determine the compressibility equation of the preform and the permeability values. The measured permeability values were converted to the principal permeability values which were involved in the simulations. The viscosity measurement and the cure kinetics of the resin system were needed for more accurate and realistic flow simulations. The cure kinetics study was based on the DSC analyses and the autocatalytic empirical model represented the cure behaviour of the resin system. Due to the shorter filling time in the 0° orientation sample, the cure and the viscosity data were not effective. However, they were very effective in the 90° orientation sample due to the longer filling time.

Normally, the infusion mesh decreases the infusion time by providing z-directional flow during the infusion process. In this study, it was not incorporated in the experiments to assess the maximum possible processability time of the resin. Elimination of the infusion mesh resulted in a

uniform and two-dimensional flow front from inlet to vent. This uniform flow front was simulated using shell elements in VARI module of PAM-RTM.

The infusion experiments were performed for two different types of preforms. All of the fabric layers were in 0° orientation in the first sample and all of the fabric layers were in 90° orientation in the second sample (Fig. 5). The main reason behind the significant difference in the filling times was the inhomogeneity of the triaxial non-crimp glass fabric. The perpendicular coarse bundles (in 90° orientation sample) to the flow direction reduced the speed of the flow front. However, the coarse bundles were parallel to the flow front for the 0° oriented sample. This parallel arrangement of the fibres resulted in long flow channels for the resin from inlet to vent, which increased the speed of the flow. Due to the longer infusion time for the 90° orientation sample, the resin cured before reaching the vent. This resulted in a 25% unimpregnated region, which was 20% in the simulation.

9 Conclusions

As a result of this study, the good agreement between the simulation and the experimental results indicates that the approach in this study can be used for the flow and the cure simulations of alternative resins such as the novel blended fire resistant resin systems in the vacuum infusion process for the global project or any other thermoset resin systems. For the novel resin systems, the cure kinetics and the viscosity modelling are needed as the inputs in the numerical simulations. The main challenge in the cure simulations is the requirement of the complex cure cycles of the blended resin systems varying from 24 to 42 hours (up to the temperature of 180°C). Also, the embedded cure monitoring methods such as thermocouples should be incorporated in the experiments for the validation of the cure simulations.

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Table 3: Thermal properties of the materials

Materials	Density (kg/m ³)	Specific heat (J/kg K)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m K)
Resin [9]	1080	2300	0.2
E-glass preform [12]	2580	1300	1.04
UP/ glass fibre Composite [13]	1690	1160	0.27
Vacuum bag	356	1256	0.069
Mould	2692	917	216.3

Table 1: Properties of the materials

FABRIC	DeVold 800-E10-H
Architecture	Triaxial, Non-crimp
Type	E glass
Nom. superficial density	829 ± 3 % (g/m ²)
Nominal construction	0°/+45°/-45°
INFUSION LIQUID	Corn oil
Density	0.925 g/cm ³
Viscosity	0.066 Pa*s (@25°C)

Table 2: Permeability and orientation angle results

V_f	Effective (10 ⁻¹¹ m ²)			Principal (10 ⁻¹¹ m ²)		Orientation angle (°)
	K_0	K_{45}	K_{90}	K'_0	K'_{90}	
0.60	2.37	1.98	1.48	2.41	1.47	9.2
0.48	3.24	2.76	2.26	3.25	2.25	5.4
0.40	6.96	5.06	3.35	7.13	3.31	3.4

Fig. 1: Vacuum infusion setup

Fig. 2: Vacuum infusion process monitoring methodology

Fig. 3: Compaction and relaxation behaviour of the preform in force control mode

Fig. 5: Fabric orientations for the permeability measurements

a) Side view

b) Top view of the base mould

Fig. 4: Preform compaction and permeability measurement test rig

Fig. 6: Principal permeability values

a) Filling time (second) b) Pressure distribution (Pa)
Fig. 7: Mould filling during a permeability test

Fig. 8: Conversion profiles as a function of time at different isothermal temperatures

Fig. 9: H_T/H_U versus isothermal temperature

Fig. 10: Cure and viscosity analysis of Crystic 701 resin with 1% MEKP content at room temperature for 24 hours

Fig. 11: Cure simulations of the Crystic 701 resin in the vacuum infusion process shown at randomly chosen times

Fig. 12: Comparison of infusion and viscosity data

Fig. 13: Unsaturated polyester resin flow front progression

Fig. 14: Resin flow front advancement results measured by thermocouples

Fig. 17: Thermocouple dipping test at room temperature

Fig. 15: Through-thickness flow front advancement

Fig. 18: Exothermic reaction monitoring during the curing stage

Fig. 16: Thermocouple flow detection phenomena test procedure

Fig. 19: Thickness and flow rate monitoring results

Fig. 20: Flow front advancement monitoring data

Fig. 21: Simulation results

Fig. 22: Resin pressure and fibre volume fraction distribution